

Leadership's Controlling via Complexity Investigation in Crisis Scenarios

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Abstract : In this paper will be discussed two coin's sides of crisis scenarios dynamics. On the one's side is negative role of subsidiary scenario branches in its compactness weakening by means unduly chaotic atomizing, having many interactive feedbacks cases, increasing a value of a complexity here. This negative role reflects the complexity of use cases, weakening leader compliancy, which brings something as a 'readiness for controlling capabilities provision'. Leader's dissatisfaction has zero compliancy, but factual it is a 'crossbar' (interface in fact) between planning and executing use cases. On the other side of this coin, an advantage of rich scenarios embranchment is possible to see in a support of response awareness, readiness, preparedness, adaptability, creativity and flexibility. Here rich scenarios embranchment contributes to the steadiness and resistance of scenario mission actors. These all will be presented in live power-points 'Blazons', modelled via DYVELOP (Dynamic Vector Logistics of Processes) on the Conference.

Keywords : leadership, controlling, complexity, DYVELOP, scenarios

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